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THE ROLE OF FARMER AND DEHKAN FARMS IN THE AGRARIAN DEVELOPMENT OF THE FERGANA REGION

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the processes of formation and development of farmer and dehkan farms in the Fergana region, their role in the agrarian economy, and their impact on production efficiency. It also highlights the strengthening of property relations, structural changes in agriculture, the emergence of new forms of entrepreneurship, and their contribution to ensuring food security.

Keywords: farmer farms, dehkan farms, agrarian reforms, Fergana region, economic efficiency, food security.

1. INTRODUCTION

The sense of ownership in farmer farms and the economically rational use of all means of production have yielded positive results. The farming movement, especially in the Yozyovon district of the Fergana region, has taken leading positions in all economic indicators. In this regard, under the leadership of the regional administration, specific measures were developed to eliminate the existing shortcomings of collective and cooperative farms and to transform them into farmer farms¹.

This process led to the formation of new economic relations in agriculture, increased production efficiency, and the improvement of land and property use systems.

2. METHODS (MATERIALS AND METHODS)

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The study employed historical, comparative-analytical, and statistical methods. The analysis was also based on archival materials of the Fergana regional administration, scientific literature, official statistical data, and interviews related to the field.

The economic efficiency of farmer and dehkan farms, production volumes, the level of land resource utilization, and changes in livestock and crop production sectors were comprehensively studied.

3. RESULTS

As a clear example of the advantages of farming, the activity of the “Ziroatchi Mustafuqul” pedigree livestock farm in the Baghdad district of the Fergana region can be highlighted. This farm began its operations in 2008 on 40 hectares of cultivated land, producing cotton and grain. In the same year, a livestock farm belonging to a former collective farm was purchased, and livestock production was launched with 60 head of cattle. In 2013, 66 head of cattle were imported from Slovakia on the basis of a preferential loan, and by 2015 their number had reached 425².

In addition, based on the resolution “On measures to improve the organization and development of the food industry management in the Republic for 2012–2015,” the processing industry in the region developed. As a result, by 2015, 100% of cotton and 70% of grain crops were directed to processing enterprises³.

Dehkan farms also made a significant contribution to increasing the country’s economic potential and ensuring food security. At the same time, they played an important role as a primary source of income for the rural population⁴.

The example of “STRAUS FARM” LLC, established in 2015, demonstrates the development of a new innovative direction in agriculture—ostrich farming. The

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enterprise imported 200 ostrich chicks from South Africa and established a modern farm. This project created 14 jobs and formed export-oriented activities⁵.

4. DISCUSSION

As a result of agricultural reforms carried out during the years of independence, the efficiency of land resource use increased. The structure of cultivated areas changed: cotton areas decreased, while vegetable growing, horticulture, and grain production expanded⁶.

In the Fergana region, while about 50% of agricultural products were produced in household subsidiary plots in 1995, the share of dehkan farms increased sharply in subsequent years. By 2004, their share in gross output reached 66.3%⁷.

Between 1991 and 2004, potato yields nearly doubled, vegetable crops increased by 117%, and melon crops by 135%. This led to a strengthening of ownership feelings and labor motivation among dehkan farmers⁸.

According to data from the FAO of the United Nations, Uzbekistan is among the leading countries in the world in the production of fruits and vegetables⁹. This confirms the high agrarian potential of the Fergana region.

CONCLUSION

In general, the development of farmer and dehkan farms in the Fergana region has contributed to increasing the efficiency of the agrarian sector. The introduction of market economy mechanisms, state support policies, and the emergence of new forms of entrepreneurship have ensured the sustainable development of agriculture.

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